

	数字普惠金融	消费支出	财政支出	地区GDP	城镇化水平	农村就业人数
响水县	54.01	7922	436672	44170	51.24	21.37
滨海县	49.24	9204	580745	34808	50.49	44.98
阜宁县	52.53	6672	564631	39411	51.69	37.21
射阳县	51.17	6687	450670	41510	54.11	34.88
建湖县	57.17	9112	658777	53178	54.76	30.53
东台市	66.32	10643	842577	61868	56.32	48.35
东海县	60.74	8370	617361	37479.92073	44.19	44.07
灌云县	49.32	7492	557402	34462.96528	43.09	38.01
灌南县	56.17	7288	525397	41235.88357	44.48	30.79
溧阳市	82.15	13701	570129	94224	58.87	31.67
常熟	80.65	17184	1380187	133150	64.12	38.78
张家港	84.84	15430	1527799	174148	71.09	30.7
昆山	84.24	15374	2229762	182222	74.19	20.85
太仓	79.19	15838	976823	150523	66.07	15.73
江阴	84.74	15304	1872766	168711	75.66	38.14
宜兴	84.93	13792	1002919	98648	56.29	34.71
丹阳市	80.56	15352	749296	103187	58.47	36.19
扬中市	80.06	13669	347116	130486	57.84	13.08
句容市	73.49	12241	436489	70684	51.65	25.42
宝应	63.68	9923	462474	55525	51.92	41.88
仪征	76.12	13389	415095	82633	52.82	22.78
高邮	64.53	10898	466428	60203	51.46	36.25
兴化市	72.88	10749	735600	49803	50.88	61.05
靖江市	79.17	9594	614900	103736	60.8	27.24
泰兴市	71.4	13963	612000	62775	55.9	56.58
海安	77.35	12447	70.58	72051	53.63	37.45
如东	69.75	10928	79.2	62631	52.62	47.86
启东	75.33	11931	74.01	77242	53.68	50.15
如皋	73.1	10225	91.29	59158	53.56	60.1
海门	69.35	12081	73.62	92697	55.62	48.99
沭阳县	58.34	8187	1004863	37523	51.65	82.32
泗阳县	58.94	8691	548419	39365	51.61	39.67
泗洪县	55.11	6362	579672	36484	51.24	38.41
涟水县	46.73	6809	540925	35843	52.28	49.41
洪泽县	60.96	9198.7	363299	61812	51.14	17.29
盱眙县	60.2	6405.2	471245	44714	51.36	32.82
金湖县	60.81	10891.8	337286	58785	51.06	13.61

就业人员平均货币工资指数	城乡可支配收入比	农村劳动力外迁数量
5794	1.814610498	2918
5691	1.791121048	13874
6554	1.662628289	7372
4212	1.620450607	10043
5733	1.75517602	5063
5370	1.678237247	8536
4916	1.902086886	5552
5509	1.793682464	8223
4480	1.99244557	5170
9911	1.94989573	1723
15467	1.959481634	2225
13519	1.975044263	2587
14741	1.961456461	2986
14616	1.965960153	979
12381	1.956186105	8379
11677	1.957181088	9418
11227	1.955671233	3610
12901	1.954228509	1329
8472	2.181966904	2686
8320	1.596167345	4856
9223	2.094414536	1806
8281	1.857830485	2132
7231	2.012273811	6774
10832	2.043693422	2871
8586	2.060135404	5698
8426	2.084922468	6464
7804	2.177245757	6094
11566	1.891659706	7171
7853	2.183391977	3823
9633	1.967966014	9987
7079	1.717111938	26582
6084	1.703079555	9113
5377	1.69995616	17411
7801	1.90876883	21375
6517	1.956591774	6394
7317	2.138943875	1450
9090	1.986200699	3789

农村劳动力非农转移数量	老龄人口负担比	女性化率	工业与服务业劳动力比例
12.34	0.7143	0.51	0.348151614
27.93	0.6541	0.517	0.251222766
21.84	0.7244	0.54	0.221445848
22.17	0.6524	0.524	0.276662844
21.07	0.5855	0.492	0.422207665
28.69	0.5682	0.51	0.308790072
24.70	0.7352	0.462446	0.299069662
19.41	0.8164	0.4804	0.262036306
14.89	0.7914	0.473206	0.289379669
23.70	0.7268	0.476791917	0.444584781
35.07	0.6400	0.493038	0.783393502
27.49	0.7500	0.475896	0.802605863
19.08	0.7200	0.498321	0.834052758
12.66	0.5200	0.490146	0.717101081
32.62	0.6500	0.470897	0.736497116
24.88	0.6000	0.477096	0.575050418
28.42	0.6510	0.485736	0.659850788
10.95	0.7485	0.495623	0.752293578
17.39	0.7915	0.473118	1.5877262
31.94	0.6896	0.473018147	0.433858644
19.40	0.7173	0.473222125	0.459174715
27.26	0.8188	0.480275862	0.493517241
40.93	0.8973	0.484848485	0.391809992
21.81	0.7750	0.482011747	0.69236417
47.56	0.8597	0.475609756	0.555850124
30.26	0.7458	0.493458	0.534312417
39.24	0.7828	0.489135	0.497910573
37.34	0.5962	0.498504	0.484346959
46.20	0.5573	0.499168	0.470881864
37.28	0.6819	0.48316	0.507858747
52.74	0.8678	0.472911	0.454081633
24.40	1.0650	0.481472	0.413410638
17.16	0.9805	0.475137	0.288206196
28.79	0.9207	0.478446	0.196114147
11.13	0.6275	0.481781	0.445922499
20.27	0.7907	0.443937	0.34369287
8.51	0.8780	0.47612	0.404114622

劳动密集型产业产值	农业机械总动力 (千瓦)	非农收入占总收入比重
712000	70.24	0.69
999500	80.96	0.64
1032700	83.18	0.65
1706100	92.04	0.41
867900	54.41	0.62
1896800	87.15	0.53
950590	148.5	0.57
844980	125.85	0.63
385240	110.12	0.68
816708	54.57	0.77
701336	33.481	0.79
548973	28.719	0.78
476111	18.1107	0.83
648392	20.0599	0.80
886120	25.13	0.80
884525	53.47	0.75
777646	41.4	0.71
216936	21.7939	0.79
636858	54.1419	0.67
616000	50.5957	0.74
211300	35.92	0.79
627200	69.0484	0.73
1558387	113.179	0.58
349978	26.5518	0.87
796694	60.5527	0.83
1027100	63.65	0.76
1268600	87.5857	0.63
1215200	54.1327	0.85
986800	83.8111	0.73
863800	34.8663	0.65
1522653	189.0679	0.82
918702	90.6732	0.88
1117236	133.9154	0.67
969354	108.8695	0.66
599567	77.6163	0.68
904168	109.6919	0.60
532029	78.821	0.75

region	Digital inclusive financial index Ce	Cf	GDP	UI	
响水县	78.06	8748	508150	48646	52.81
滨海县	73.58	10137	694488	38359	52.1
阜宁县	75.61	7386	715056	43315	53.5
射阳县	76.35	7330	593838	45737	55.7
建湖县	82.30	9854	836409	58483	56.45
东台市	88.76	11576	1017151	67916	57.89
东海县	86.97	9092	687167	40844.8365	45.04
灌云县	75.10	8181	618031	37469.4132	44.24
灌南县	77.21	7972	609084	44568.7609	46
溧阳市	102.74	15003	613800.00	97010.1196	59.00
常熟	111.45	18686	1552550	135431	73.21
张家港	114.86	16623	1713442	177987	72.27
昆山	131.75	16819	2553588	186582	75.16
太仓	113.35	17333	1090697	155159	67.52
江阴	114.45	16716	2053514	176119	77.26
宜兴	108.91	14999	1091081	102652	60.46
丹阳市	102.29	16701	800700	109276	57.35
扬中市	103.46	14890	385260	139184	64.60
句容市	96.88	13369	494889	75020	46.73
宝应	86.68	10813	530155	60669	47.28
仪征	98.70	14632	468268	88947	52.66
高邮	86.73	11984	536214	65421	47.89
兴化市	83.99	10464	825000	53186	52.44
靖江市	100.13	15124	699500	108973	62.22
泰兴市	93.67	10630	674500	68781	57.22
海安	96.86	13559.00	842200.00	78551.00	55.32
如东	89.44	11960.00	937900.00	68506.00	54.29
启东	94.78	13083.00	862800.00	84099.00	55.34
如皋	92.76	11182.00	1005100.00	64761.00	55.27
海门	87.16	13124.00	855600.00	101298.00	57.32
沭阳县	78.17	9030	1126910	40719	54.09
泗阳县	80.71	9512	694620	43072	53.86
泗洪县	76.30	7005	669597	40394	53.76
涟水县	72.34	7443.8	628491	40290	49.79924
洪泽县	81.41	10090.9	477833	68459	50.68128
盱眙县	82.14	7072.8	575185	49145	50.3908
金湖县	86.60	11938	411372	65476	50.87613

Nre	Ieamw	Rurdi	Nrle	
21.38		5818	1.806387531	2403
44.53		5140	1.786961924	10666
37.15		7180	1.664167492	13605
34.86		4656	1.616014799	5674
30.42		6411	1.746222987	4503
48.25		6033	1.675968393	2180
43.94		5362	1.902830047	7207
38.01		6187	1.787728306	8248
30.06		4897	1.986062412	9753
31.76		11445	1.933853119	2777
38.76		16983	1.953159506	1871
30.45		14531	1.968423099	2079
20.8		16060	1.953537609	2832
15.53		15796	1.955075459	1061
38.12		16044	1.949138859	9545
34.55		13469	1.951163852	5870
36.12		12187	1.939171526	1755
13.51		14029	1.937631363	2636
25.87		9320	2.163526361	1607
41.69		9110	1.595795447	1895
23.14		9977	2.094931218	2344
36.05		9080	1.858470015	3169
61.03		8084	2.007470857	8015
27.25		11819	2.038791909	2785
56.45		8868	2.061981454	5640
37.45		9168	2.081394646	6184
47.46		8705	2.169583623	5924
50.18		12607	1.890195221	3049
60.1		8622	2.175637394	3975
49.01		10530	1.970083219	7413
82.3		7624	1.707727975	10826
40.3		6623	1.696875	3728
38.34		5873	1.698405065	9310
50.14		5951	1.902682155	9686
16.84		7916	1.954800453	8541
33.42		9783	2.13305102	1088
13.62		8676	1.982567254	2939

Nntrl	Reb	Rf	Plfis
12.42	0.7032	52.10	0.351262862
27.95	0.6263	50.90	0.253986077
22.07	0.6875	54.00	0.229878869
22.23	0.6186	51.20	0.277395295
21.12	0.7936	49.72	0.42504931
28.76	0.5976	52.77	0.312746114
24.72	0.7415	0.46	0.301775148
19.41	0.8146	0.48	0.262562484
14.63	0.7932	0.47	0.304391218
23.80	0.61	0.48	0.446473552
35.14	0.77	0.49	0.785345717
27.31	0.89	0.49	0.805582923
19.08	0.87	0.48	0.832211538
12.57	0.67	0.49	0.722472634
32.74	0.64	0.47	0.735309549
24.89	0.57	0.48	0.577424023
28.86	0.65	0.49	0.672203765
11.44	0.71	0.49	0.763878608
18.05	0.76	0.47	0.429454967
31.59	0.71	0.47	0.42816023
19.83	0.70	0.47	0.46326707
26.98	0.80	0.48	0.490707351
41.05	0.89	0.48	0.393904637
21.83	0.77	0.48	0.68733945
47.64	0.86	0.48	0.564038973
30.47	0.74	0.49	0.536715621
39.10	0.86	0.48	0.512010114
37.83	0.76	0.50	0.481666002
46.60	0.56	0.50	0.472545757
37.43	0.66	0.48	0.51009998
53.75	0.86	0.47	0.468529769
24.92	1.05	0.48	0.427791563
17.95	0.97	0.47	0.302556077
29.67	0.88	0.47	0.219984045
10.82	0.63	0.48	0.447149644
20.52	0.77	0.45	0.350089767
8.64	0.89	0.47	0.410425844

Vlio	Ptam	Pniti	
	732500	74.09	0.71
	1072500	85.04	0.59
	1068500	83.83	0.65
	1763300	99.84	0.42
	898100	58.84	0.62
	1963200	92.05	0.54
	1062500	159.15	0.58
	955740	127.2	0.64
	401460	118.75	0.69
	858519	55.24	0.77
	761975	32.3023	0.80
	593227	29.81	0.79
	523747	17.9916	0.83
	701340	20.7684	0.80
	890314	25.5629	0.80
	892161	53.9648	0.75
	844119	37.0274	0.71
	235347	13.5779	0.80
	703681	55.0824	0.68
	656300	54.5858	0.75
	222900	39.08	0.79
	663400	70.8619	0.75
	1643039	116.03	0.60
	363802	27.9499	0.88
	834670	61.9501	0.82
	1081200	64.6	0.77
	1333500	91.785	0.64
	1278500	56.8912	0.85
	1041900	85.3142	0.73
	908500	37.1061	0.66
	1606850	205.8682	0.82
	988135	95.2575	0.88
	1140265	143.6274	0.67
	1025166	118.2217	0.68
	638077	83.646	0.70
	969117	120.1175	0.63
	580912	86.9461	0.76

region	digital inclusive financial index	Ce	Cf	GDP	UI
响水县	95.37720703	9651	501274	53971	54.09
滨海县	89.07550476	11225	708929	41761	53.55
阜宁县	92.64095165	8275	765450	47236	54.79
射阳县	93.98673738	8161	645980	49749	56.91
建湖县	95.79782417	10989	732172	63514	57.74
东台市	98.0262053	12771	955830	73902	59.63
赣榆县	93.33100069	10694	602247	53885	51.57
东海县	93.51071732	10194	580905	44871	45.86
灌云县	90.64148643	9140	496431	40926	45.33
灌南县	92.68879172	8978	480435	48429	47.42
武进区	104.6517777	17655	1454400	136916	67
新北区	105.294061	17946	582200	167566	61.148159
溧阳市	99.25168755	16895	694400	105256	60.018382
金坛市	98.82623461	14172	529800	107242	61
浦口区	107.6862575	16700	1129790.8	114957.79	85.416371
江宁	109.1319577	17846	2166926.8	143768.2	83.24637
六合	101.1890721	16214	1015904.8	114271.8	72.889509
溧水	102.7134055	14903	528513.71	148538.73	92.026282
高淳	102.6671743	15881	262298.64	136396.38	58.069863
常熟	96.84871639	21024	1587404	139768	74.313792
张家港	103.8183329	18687	1848059	184744	71.53724
昆山	104.8495368	18890	2690029	191058	85.967407
吴江	102.2132449	17723	1592870	125420	81.95553
太仓	98.85468667	19589	1158414	162523	70.991672
江阴	100.1681535	18791	2262583	188101	60.121766
宜兴	101.8448332	16771	1174161	109881	64.934412
京口区	104.0557834	17429	164502	113230	81.234455
润州区	105.7944772	17485	185607	121242	79.49188
丹徒区	98.67034788	14072	292421	120448	66.874672
丹阳市	97.19285571	18791	790060	115816	69.717577
扬中市	102.3426392	16574	386599	147431	71.628871
句容市	98.73779283	14484	535355	78862	74.22668
宝应	96.41613745	12145	643833	66961	52.709059
仪征	100.0759956	16390	546153	98555	65.034499
高邮	97.62020652	13280	569262	72563	68.029973
海陵区	107.2206892	15563	271500	107903	91.53
高港区	103.3322956	14593	350900	167416	64.45
兴化市	95.10395297	11691	850200	59662	54.03
靖江市	99.27907428	16958	641500	116703	63.76
泰兴市	98.8980921	11935	763800	77315	59.04
姜堰市	94.1771635	13096	668800	79829	59.4
通州区	92.10031028	14748	857500	89904	59.404553
海安	99.77041191	15120	813500	87201	57.113164
如东	95.18197726	13314	1021600	76046	56.070483
启东	98.39629156	14615	890300	92534	57.121849
如皋	95.93200466	12526	963800	72255	57.048
海门	91.17966376	14570	857500	111100	59.104972
沭阳县	88.83881895	10044	1215138	45530	55.3
泗阳县	92.69127316	10599	726494	48431	55.13
泗洪县	92.51122909	7777	689372	45439	55.04
宿豫区	90.69988877	9943	399904	57086	63.46
宿城区	96.60584046	9454	424281	47251	62.58
淮安区	93.4330153	9504.7	679382	45408	51.633789
淮阴区	91.99115363	12210.5	627121	55794	51.529111
涟水县	91.99576438	8324.1	641113	45680	51.521226
洪泽县	95.20373023	11293.7	414811	75558	52.365464

盱眙县	92.78972057	7937.7	546490	54625	52.425402
金湖县	96.37827566	13384.5	418407	72987	52.561784

Nre	Ieamw	Rurdi	Nrle	
21.57		6651	1.78781733	4180
44.09		5614	1.777710803	8052
36.76		7950	1.654446532	12399
34.64		4908	1.60310837	4671
30.31		6941	1.734882632	8452
48.23		6661	1.656916916	5527
45		7096	1.846378386	6575
43.8		5822	1.89072962	8600
38.9		6448	1.771840543	7957
29.9		5347	1.970555109	6172
37.87		12890	1.898353812	3190
21.64		15694	1.957672172	1851
31.73		12820	1.920772638	3069
20.97		14400	1.942331013	2004
12.5		11863	2.201291762	7130
29.17		15858	2.236324255	5920
28.65		16703	2.237647287	11549
18.1		11470	2.13472155	4730
22.17		10519	2.135969279	2185
38.42		18330	1.946308485	1523
30.42		15703	1.960644906	1463
20.78		17402	1.94222443	2394
29.87		15765	1.979051297	1112
15.52		17115	1.948390117	847
39.28		16854	1.938575636	7424
35.68		14581	1.944071871	8548
1.98		14582	1.786346236	2413
1.65		14587	1.761831866	2946
15.35		11760	2.156812068	9363
36.48		13398	1.918962499	2643
13.66		15339	1.921693565	3733
25.97		10145	2.14799132	5096
41.78		9921	1.592429995	3668
23.02		10772	2.085122174	4516
36.52		9805	1.854058518	1996
11.99		11803	1.916637302	1790
13.35		11180	2.005063291	1008
60.97		8934	1.987230269	8392
26.96		12777	2.02565672	2919
56.73		9578	2.046911781	5941
34.76		9347	2.096596398	2481
52.6		11582	2.044307291	3699
37.32		10018	2.074591167	2115
47.59		9496	2.169110345	4121
49.22		13731	1.881257862	4031
60		9424	2.16726885	5051
48.88		11478	1.965692935	1458
82.01		8196	1.696533636	22050
40.81		7172	1.686854931	3247
38.32		6413	1.684623853	14179
20.12		6290	1.677274988	5024
24.46		7321	1.88262063	5879
43.39		7407	1.799829267	6440
39.44		9723	2.117883996	3554
49.48		7688	1.88680741	1349
16.69		8463	1.929719055	1194

33.9
13.45

8174
8651

2.116816369
1.963871247

3755
1173

Nntrl	Reb	Rf	Plfis	
12.69		0.6875	0.513	0.35
27.97		0.6473	0.52	0.26
22.01		0.7062	0.53	0.24
22.14		0.6224	0.533	0.28
21.10		0.7777	0.522	0.43
29.22		0.5799	0.55	0.32
26.10		0.5842	442222222	0.29
24.70		0.7391	461187215	0.31
18.70		0.8040	483290488	0.24
14.70		0.7941	473154362	0.31
31.14		0.8	480855558	0.66
19.12		0.92	476432532	0.74
23.91		0.85	476520643	0.45
15.91		0.75	460181211	0.48
10.20		0.64	0.4856	0.56
23.79		0.60	484744601	0.55
22.63		0.73	477137871	0.45
14.32		0.79	440331492	0.50
17.96		0.78	470455571	0.44
34.84		0.72	493492972	0.79
27.37		0.86	476988823	0.81
19.11		0.89	489412897	0.84
26.17		0.73	492802143	0.77
12.65		0.71	490335052	0.73
33.44		0.83	0.476578	0.72
25.53		0.75	0.473094	0.56
1.80		0.80	0.504762	0.73
1.51		0.91	0.468599	0.67
11.92		0.69	0.494808	0.62
29.36		0.63	0.485565	0.68
11.65		0.72	0.496778	0.77
18.39		0.76	0.473277	0.44
31.48		0.734322642	0.471039	0.42
19.84		0.696785404	0.470895	0.47
27.54		0.787787514	0.480285	0.49
5.89		0.459549625	0.508757	0.62
6.7		0.792509363	0.498127	0.52
31.42		0.888797769	0.484665	0.40
14.13		0.835311573	0.47589	0.69
29.52		0.848404724	0.47964	0.58
16.79		0.776467204	0.516974	0.48
41.35		0.579692015	0.478707	0.51
30.45		0.744560557	0.493837	0.53
39.48		0.856068502	0.485816	0.53
37.17		0.789774482	0.488419	0.47
46.8		0.52629	0.501667	0.48
37.31		0.672193126	0.48302	0.51
53.71		0.857090599	0.472869	0.47
25.86		1.049252634	0.481745	0.44
17.96		0.9532881	0.474948	0.30
14.23		0.865308151	0.477634	0.47
15.84		0.947260834	0.477514	0.42
21.64		0.945148652	0.484213	0.27
24.55		0.947261663	0.490872	0.39
29.1		0.920371867	0.460792	0.23
10.32		0.650089874	0.484122	0.43

20.56	0.745132743	0.453982	0.35
8.85	0.908550186	0.477323	0.42

Vlio	Ptam	Pniti	
751300		75.48	0.736624939
1106900		84.52	0.592391668
1104100		84.02	0.658462336
1810700		102.03	0.41817852
929900		61.84	0.617280337
2031100		94	0.539666447
293410		32.5	0.532889824
1256500		151.66	0.532270311
1079130		126.49	0.539440204
420910		124.14	0.693563958
686302		26.44	0.646187776
343552		12.04	0.810843716
897247		55.86	0.783095118
697586		43.99	0.770042668
770981		25.74	0.694623856
1064583		51.09	0.853357298
1060118		58.32	0.928526403
731303		33.06	0.72527845
732527		53.01	0.612003982
798014		32.0311	0.80329804
611401		29.99	0.792272613
545148		17.995	0.834516289
770100		25.15	0.708066161
694824		20.85	0.802996471
786676		25.6261	0.802845889
773836		52.1475	0.764182378
28440		5.732	0.782900893
28157		2.4792	0.782880469
352123		21.4642	0.782899942
866404		37.3484	0.722841611
255344		13.6496	0.797987843
733244		56.2638	0.69184354
664400		58.3649	0.753203607
233600		40.22	0.79761361
695900		71.3573	0.752123643
135256		7.9826	0.754039768
203704		11.604	0.756261783
1799381		119.76	0.609399941
398110		28.3887	0.875796991
917649		62.571	0.816388297
683549		42.23	0.733223479
976400		50.1962	0.721059762
1132900		65.5489	0.774390922
1398800		92.434	0.648051872
1317300		59.2811	0.854389937
1088800		81.1195	0.740093585
941200		38.1918	0.661248059
1725633		207.9543	0.81492615
1065285		99.0798	0.878611806
1218867		148.4475	0.670259521
498767		62.8414	0.754085473
404842		43.494	0.873901957
1096680		100.6304	0.755397367
1281228		78.498	0.689178303
1094878		119.1228	0.718215063
670753		85.8299	0.71039052

1007527
625625

123.5683
87.0723

0.73198394
0.711977453

region	Digital inclusive financial index	Ce	Cf	GDP	UI
响水县	109.3236353	10487	550081.00	63854	56.15
滨海县	107.0403772	12161	753553.00	47355	56.00
阜宁县	107.6501757	8988	736547.00	53745	56.63
射阳县	107.4839003	8887	751108.00	56531	57.95
建湖县	109.3175529	11872	744419.00	71589	58.80
东台市	112.2637095	13700	949430.00	82906	60.65
赣榆县	105.2383966	11481	615787.00	60574	52.94
东海县	107.9270384	10897	619818.00	49891	46.63
灌云县	104.368064	9804	548464.00	45405	46.35
灌南县	107.187512	9607	501895.00	53794	48.81
武进区	118.482678	15206	1565578.00	156789	67.12
新北区	121.6281994	19281	611293.00	193987	64.97
溧阳市	114.8020518	18133	816341.00	112589	60.21
金坛市	115.4463055	15206	675289.00	126376	62.00
浦口区	122.5194678	18170	1303207.20	769153731	71.31
江宁	124.890427	19426	2499537.62	794553464	56.81
六合	116.2328344	17559	1171840.30	422937208	48.65
溧水	114.7046087	16215	609637.52	190148739	58.28
常熟	114.0231821	22757	1658019	150532	58.34
张家港	115.9023917	20227	1936161	207380	67.24
昆山	121.5840085	20408	2930442	212103	74.09
吴江	117.9404447	19163	1743596	137419	65.00
太仓	115.3644932	20919	1265111	173835	73.61
江阴	115.1974898	20372	2272879	211943	70.2
宜兴	115.3215503	18161	1236372	124208	65.2
京口区	121.0830984	18649	165153	118377	99.41
润州区	120.4464157	18685	153736	81834	92.34
丹徒区	115.1428063	14938	271966	126486	72.09
丹阳市	113.6553387	20207	828816	125422	63.47
扬中市	116.2146729	17860	412525	156349	76.01
句容市	115.0124057	15556	601002	84683	59.82
宝应	109.6647614	13130	677903.00	75828	50.15
仪征	112.9137412	17488	575031.00	110871	56.62
高邮	110.8293273	14238	652584.00	81908	59.74
海陵区	121.5088671	17180	326700	124358	92.03
高港区	116.2520497	16062	387800	195296	66.22
兴化市	109.8378241	12847	906100	68679	56.04
靖江市	114.6690975	18482	702100	134364	65.55
泰兴市	111.6472579	13168	818400	89456	60.94
姜堰市	111.4581947	14334	657700.00	91492	61.30
通州区	108.8926227	16067	1006500	102400	61.30
海安	112.9455431	16451	864700	100295	58.98
如东	109.8830427	14431	1081000	86897	57.89
启东	113.179377	15715	926700	103950	59.00
如皋	110.6356152	13649	1094100	82149	58.88
海门	110.2881474	15957	937900	125445	61.03
沭阳县	105.5776479	10874	1370822.93	49463	55.71
泗阳县	106.4971951	11665	653053	53092	56.7
泗洪县	106.4068946	8525	706643	49884	56.36
宿豫区	107.344826	10848	387459	62509	64.62
宿城区	111.4741613	10288	395926	51220	62.75
淮安区	108.0678978	10363	691046	50501	53.21
淮阴区	109.5017967	13336.3	571243	61718	53.12
涟水县	105.3153393	9125.6	583525	50599	53.10
洪泽县	110.3744712	12256.9	366639	83894	53.94
盱眙县	108.0581425	8651.1	502566	60441	54.04

金湖县

110.1513071

14599

448479

80696

54.14

Nre	Ieamw	Rurdi	Nrle
21.75	10820	1.312706348	7465
43.7	7067	1.852110869	3051
36.8	6129	1.704791155	10686
34.6	8691	1.710148368	3544
30.42	5460	1.780945527	5866
48.46	7898	1.904608096	6093
46.6	7824	1.835337134	8511
43.8	6404	1.873693489	7937
38.8	7126	1.75911742	11431
30.6	5877	1.952855781	8436
21.5	15584	2.16180481	3150
20.96	16666	1.958920495	2175
32.07	14050	1.918984686	3680
37.8	15584	1.936988679	1482
9.47	12941	2.148052059	5118
28.3	17126	2.22739899	3906
25.81	18203	2.18125388	4580
17.85	12783	2.13476372	1192
38.41	19735	1.948461437	1582
30.36	16974	1.961044123	2075
20.91	18877	1.941388698	2752
29.83	17121	1.977213148	1365
15.29	18550	1.946912676	939
35.79	17218	1.937802961	5559
35.96	15810	1.942231231	4199
1.97	15715	1.796320321	3428
0.51	15726	1.772539776	6580
14.81	12706	2.164535421	2893
36.57	14627	1.912934796	3719
13.65	16728	1.921760958	4063
26.35	11017	2.144249038	3648
41.41	10834	1.587466797	1031
23.04	11670	2.085115326	3414
36.91	10672	1.850870553	2121
12.13	12861	1.915578121	2153
13.34	12076	2.000246403	1185
60.73	9854	1.975900352	11040
23.76	13845	2.020130144	3648
57	10549	2.040922161	8467
34.91	10353	2.091159933	3241
52.19	12665	2.035697899	12285
37.18	10959	2.0700611	13324
47.55	10463	2.163250013	12274
48.98	14971	1.87907427	1693
60.54	10266	2.162053837	5080
48.96	12505	1.960381968	8134
80.52	8974	1.670821493	16264
40.13	7750	1.673394495	20764
38.3	7007	1.671441001	6012
20.08	6886	1.660216167	1973
25.34	7991	1.86439224	6205
43.24	8055	1.795869387	1143
38.82	7683	2.103688525	6850
49.91	7322	1.883249777	6380
16.42	8230	1.927236511	4146
34.4	6967	2.119401091	4720

13.41

7477

1.956615672

3529

Nntrl	Reb	Rf	Plfis
12.99	0.693	0.51	0.3522
27.94	0.6631	0.52	0.2590
22.20	0.7941	0.54	0.2410
22.32	0.6333	0.53	0.2824
21.26	0.7561	0.54	0.4287
29.67	0.5609	0.53	0.3155
27.80	0.5983	0.42	0.3004
24.90	0.7421	0.46	0.3059
18.70	0.8040	0.48	0.2139
15.90	0.7941	0.48	0.3170
19.05	0.78	0.48	0.7526
15.91	0.91	0.45	0.5010
24.28	0.72	0.48	0.4524
31.18	0.62	0.48	0.6614
7.71	0.660633484	0.49	0.5480
23.21	0.581824636	0.47	0.5353
20.56	0.727025979	0.47	0.4599
14.17	0.779988944	0.43	0.4947
34.94	0.78	0.49	0.8006
27.45	0.93	0.49	0.8205
19.27	0.94	0.49	0.8388
26.21	0.74	0.49	0.7680
12.58	0.68	0.49	0.7345
31.11	0.84	0.47	0.7536
28.00	0.77	0.47	0.6215
1.81	0.802030457	0.50	0.7462
0.47	0.9432	0.48	0.7843
11.45	0.71910871	0.50	0.6144
30.06	0.638501504	0.48	0.6962
11.70	0.757509158	0.50	0.7766
18.99	0.752941176	0.48	0.4539
31.18	0.75319971	0.46	0.4291
19.89	0.69921875	0.47	0.4688
28.17	0.77567055	0.48	0.4996
11.04	0.450948063	0.50	0.6208
11.64	0.804347826	0.52	0.5247
41.24	0.893462868	0.48	0.3991
19.21	0.738215488	0.48	0.7066
48.63	0.841754386	0.48	0.5811
29.23	0.782870238	0.52	0.4864
41.03	0.555769304	0.48	0.5175
30.39	0.722296934	0.49	0.5334
39.68	0.839245005	0.49	0.5384
37.52	0.80919559	0.49	0.4712
47.49	0.510305583	0.50	0.4871
37.73	0.659524101	0.48	0.5165
52.95	0.849602583	0.48	0.4857
25.83	1.042362322	0.48	0.4463
17.98	0.938120104	0.47	0.3039
14.27	0.864541833	0.48	0.4766
15.95	0.863456985	0.48	0.4167
21.55	0.944958372	0.48	0.2752
24.44	0.978361669	0.46	0.3936
29.48	0.924063314	0.46	0.2484
10.07	0.678440926	0.49	0.4172
18.49	0.758139535	0.44	0.3564

8.83

0.88888889

0.48

0.4176

Vlio	Ptam	Pniti	
	770500	75.59	0.817847373
	1149800	86.19	0.571089439
	1144300	85.35	0.647542998
	1876700	105.45	0.384985163
	955900	63.88	0.6284876
	2108900	95.2	0.491225237
	349210	25.76	0.665468518
	1481200	152.15	0.583490744
	1206830	128.33	0.615627855
	457490	129.28	0.705476941
	714319	25.56	0.771506487
	361111	12.04	0.804134116
	939516	54.91	0.784518565
	732892	45	0.771506487
	758387	26.1	0.692029602
	1105776	51.48	0.855176768
	1031631	59.31	0.928881795
	772815	33.49	0.737343736
	784745	31.95	0.804311939
	606459	29.71	0.796806678
	555129	17.75	0.838761521
	790263	25.48	0.71103045
	687939	20.94	0.806401119
	808204	26.1892	0.810526661
	873922	48.9943	0.769470648
	24860	5.7314	0.7858238
	12521	2.4792	0.78581811
	364300	21.9309	0.785821948
	875430	37.9359	0.733762657
	272938	13.8654	0.8
	763373	57.0074	0.697276757
	657900	60.0929	0.754431615
	315200	41.55	0.79771975
	715400	72.0249	0.751757327
	143505	8.2195	0.754627279
	218504	11.9845	0.752661147
	2062794	122.35	0.620741944
	414826	27.748	0.875520809
	964550	62.684	0.818391867
	748450	43.41	0.739014994
	1020900	50.998	0.721437093
	1190600	68.8263	0.77892057
	1480000	93.8484	0.654980464
	1379400	61.8841	0.854732377
	1144700	85.065	0.73974977
	999900	38.6084	0.661558961
	1765235	211.6662	0.813307985
	1109075	102.9087	0.879356679
	1301182	157.3369	0.668688316
	516191	63.3845	0.754477592
	418491	44.019	0.873446179
	1154860	102.0081	0.770887367
	1333701	80.8529	0.713698303
	1149753	123.8912	0.732445063
	693768	89.3999	0.74865052
	1040673	125.8063	0.74639694

662581

83.4112

0.738475453

region	Digital inclusive financial index Ce	Cf	GDP	
响水县	110.3643617	11132	615414.00	70112
滨海县	107.3535856	12637	809997.00	50994
阜宁县	108.8630331	9608	865203.00	58271
射阳县	107.8671946	9405	851088.00	60875
建湖县	110.2759751	12443	873440.00	77196
东台市	113.2122139	14632	1153415.00	90084
赣榆县	109.9909242	12233	695891.00	62775
东海县	108.3790535	11324	667483.00	50916
灌云县	105.9419513	10515	565708.00	46374
灌南县	109.8431583	10235	534079.00	55397
武进区	123.503142	20430	1710643	164510
新北区	126.5677653	20592	688662	210528
溧阳市	117.4423385	19403	871708	122626
金坛市	119.897101	16270	736609.00	142819
浦口区	128.4582348	19534	1475256.81	135221.8
江宁	128.7966505	20922	2829526.95	501669644
六合	119.7629303	18893	1326546.83	277191925
溧水	118.7637568	17478	690121.96	895837735
高淳	118.5156338	18679	342503.98	759621729
常熟	119.1245044	24374	1831208	158334
张家港	119.0156505	21645	2119909	216023
昆山	125.1945228	21851	3184901	230270
吴江	120.4577313	20467	1930641	147302
太仓	119.3691991	22216	1325917	185465
江阴	118.1016646	21632	2304834	230538
宜兴	118.2868945	19432	1406999	136473
丹阳市	117.1967849	21925	916517	126736
扬中市	116.8118728	19342	420297	157742
句容市	117.9867681	17155	697999	91077
宝应	110.5602682	14036	717623	83032
仪征	114.3242384	15321	660347	118401
高邮	111.2083746	15306	741886	89970
兴化市	111.9721519	13756	1055000	72422
靖江市	117.3336294	19877	811500	146061
泰兴市	113.7766807	14059	963400	97697
通州区	114.4885087	17252	1161600	111135
海安	114.9318264	17575	1124900	114798
如东	111.4632302	15426	1191800	97232
启东	115.4682244	16683	952300	111824
如皋	112.814896	14741	1076900	90031
海门	114.5638686	17121	1027100	137958
沭阳县	109.1024448	11608	1098016	56189
泗阳县	107.9271737	12494	671345	55207
泗洪县	107.1429565	9109	749650	51447
宿豫区	106.8359983	11572	379011	63099
宿城区	114.3638468	10957	393893	57956
淮安区	112.2760435	11171	758895	57600.84
淮阴区	111.3892397	14150	675981	68019.85
涟水县	105.027481	9902	629779	56044.95
洪泽县	109.7304789	13103	387699	94276.67
盱眙县	109.3228439	9440	549738	67175.04
金湖县	111.0581742	15577	407766	89002.7

UI	Nre	Ieamw	Rurdi	
	57.36	21.73	7496	1.77
	57.1	43.36	6687	1.76
	57.79	36.28	9499	1.65
	58.98	34.56	5920	1.59
	59.85	30.07	8519	1.73
	61.68	48.5	8561	1.64
	54.31	43.5	8504	1.82
	47.39	43.5	6958	1.86
	47.53	38.8	7917	1.75
	50.22	31.1	6405	1.94
67.87093216		37.82	15581	1.90
67.30602827		21.31	17945	1.95
60.40875147		32.14	15398	1.91
62.5088968		20.95	16825	1.93
77.51250508		9.19	14054	2.14
80.9549851		27.74	18616	2.22
69.35193582		25.78	19893	2.17
62.52454958		17.9	14119	2.12
55.4236915		22.04	12730	2.12
72.99191296		38.38	21100	1.94
77.31969303		31.77	18318	1.96
82.15643985		20.92	20257	1.94
67.60697888		29.81	18437	1.97
68.53354267		15.19	20085	1.94
70.7		36.02	18591	1.93
65.3		36.14	17160	1.93
66.7665493		36.58	15874	1.90
57.45748503		13.64	18048	1.90
58.60738385		26.58	12019	2.13
67.36716034		40.87	11831	1.58
56.11662565		23.08	12685	2.07
59.73860706		36.83	11565	1.84
57.24		60.65	10721	1.97
66.17		31.03	15049	2.01
62.15		56.91	11522	2.03
62.29307174		52.08	13836	2.02
60.16194332		37.18	11979	2.05
58.81451201		47.44	11743	2.15
59.82105263		47.99	16157	1.87
59.61987598		60.75	11241	2.14
62.34110755		48.73	13585	1.94
57.76		78.89	9799	1.66
58.21		40.6	8453	1.66
57.71		38.31	7648	1.66
65.17		20.11	7487	1.65
63.59		23.53	8698	1.88
53.21748289		43.92	8039	1.79
54.32680071		38.19	9493	2.09
54.31866321		49.82	7094	1.87
55.09342978		16.51	8130	1.92
59.5890411		34.25	7759	2.10
55.33193151		13.18	8183	1.94

Nrle	Nntrl	Reb	Rf
	7304	13.06	0.69 48.90
	3146	28.00	0.65 49.70
	14255	21.96	0.68 54.00
	3097	22.44	0.73 53.70
	5793	20.98	0.85 48.90
	6051	30.10	0.68 49.40
	9195	28.10	0.6035 0.44
	9498	24.80	0.7465 0.46
	11934	19.10	0.8093 0.48
	8292	17.00	0.7911 0.49
	3820	31.35	0.81 0.48
	2686	18.93	0.79 0.48
	3754	24.50	0.85 0.48
	1837	15.91	0.66 0.46
	3324	7.54	0.720994475 0.46
	4504	22.71	0.593286219 0.48
	4798	20.60	0.73255814 0.47
	3025	14.22	0.783112583 0.43
	5457	17.99	0.797709924 0.47
	1503	34.96	0.72 0.49
	2247	28.65	0.87 0.48
	3173	19.32	0.69 0.49
	1273	26.22	0.61 0.49
	1055	12.50	0.75 0.49
	8099	32.07	0.6642 0.47
	3926	28.25	0.6078 0.47
	5195	30.29	0.651175506 0.48
	6783	11.74	0.764662757 0.49
	5092	19.45	0.756583898 0.48
	2811	30.82	0.779055542 0.465378
	3884	19.95	0.695407279 0.470971
	2695	28.03	0.774640239 0.480858
	13096	41.32	0.895630668 0.48
	3892	26.1	0.711569449 0.48
	8910	48.57	0.837989808 0.48
	5952	40.93	0.553861367 0.48
	8307	30.55	0.706842388 0.49
	7156	39.82	0.835798904 0.49
	2846	37.48	0.852140029 0.49
	4006	47.79	0.520992593 0.50
	11796	37.63	0.649819413 0.48
	21093	52.09	0.850171124 0.48
	7193	26.61	1.042857143 0.48
	6479	18.02	0.927173062 0.48
	2973	14.33	0.851317752 0.48
	2716	13.76	1.087547811 0.46
	2018	22.26	0.965619308 0.48
	9795	24.16	0.975124378 0.46
	5920	29.53	0.925331192 0.46
	17180	10.42	0.506965475 0.49
	3727	20.77	0.851970803 0.43
	4472	8.73	0.886191199 0.47

Plfis**Vlio****Ptam**

0.352508053	802300	76.86
0.259686347	1206600	89.36
0.256339581	1202500	85.77
0.286168981	1968100	106.83
0.427668773	1002700	65.76
0.314845361	2195400	97.86
0.326436782	439000	39.41
0.310344828	1669580	163.82
0.24742268	1334840	128.95
0.340836013	492090	132.21
0.658910629	677536	25.42
0.766776161	375725	11.79
0.457373989	947055	55.91
0.507875895	755485	44.76
0.561479869	792917	26.16
0.546863735	1149503	52.01
0.460822343	1079997	56.1
0.497206704	808566	34.29
0.44600726	803973	54.04
0.801719646	750944	31.7
0.82090022	597777	30.15
0.840344168	568708	17.93
0.768534049	774068	20.58
0.735352205	669694	21.12
0.773736813	675689	26.65
0.624792474	893648	48.25
0.699015856	838540	38.45
0.781524927	289305	14.03
0.459744169	788140	57.61
0.436261316	1327257	60.96
0.466637782	472158	41.72
0.497149063	1488313	73.52
0.400659522	2210192	124.58
0.719948437	427332	27.93
0.583552978	1015471	62.95
0.519393241	1034600	48.2225
0.537385691	1253200	69.9648
0.542790894	1567100	94.564
0.479474891	1448100	63.3632
0.492510288	1205700	87.5448
0.519597784	1063400	39.4752
0.493218405	1848037	214.2958
0.453694581	1171810	106.1891
0.304098147	1387214	162.4002
0.480358031	521740	63.8036
0.357416065	421799	44.566
0.300091075	1205808	124.022
0.38832155	1398244	89.886
0.253914091	1232159	123.15
0.428225318	725831	60.721
0.361459854	1088679	140.718
0.403641882	695548	80.88

Pniti

0.752173913
0.598106616
0.663877038
0.435200733
0.637831946
0.617618047
0.667541657
0.586432248
0.62802556
0.713476325
0.657915912
0.803551724
0.785317277
0.770345851
0.690841034
0.854621136
0.92916007
0.738998421
0.620715646
0.80749543
0.799993877
0.842903147
0.71156116
0.809384435
0.809904635
0.77333094
0.735068076
0.793999787
0.70201228
0.759481088
0.797370456
0.747318769
0.625485897
0.877002584
0.817989468
0.724255141
0.780282215
0.679992152
0.845442648
0.745065953
0.660825829
0.810844255
0.879640721
0.674439136
0.755644189
0.87362474
0.787371367
0.719359303
0.733993063
0.75510565
0.75695844
0.748831953

region	Digital inclusive financial index Ce		Cf	GDP
响水县	115.1498229	12087	644686.00	77661
滨海县	112.7521544	12554	813481.00	52939
阜宁县	114.2767224	10331	900965.00	67264
射阳县	113.6870737	10080	916788.00	64186
建湖县	115.514473	13401	934490.00	78279
东台市	118.8622857	15657	1087027.00	86850
赣榆县	115.5675772	13100	756219.00	64477
东海县	115.5223696	12140	700454.00	54273
灌云县	113.5226976	11378	627506.00	44664
灌南县	115.1508101	10993	573257.00	60036
武进区	130.5499934	21942	1787549.00	171023
新北区	131.8331761	22013	708992.00	222441
溧阳市	123.4652383	20897	1019095.00	132322
金坛市	125.063349	17425	811356.00	161439
浦口区	134.7913981	21131	1596427.86	138015
江宁	135.9056185	22596	3061931.74	176012
六合	125.5220633	20424	1435503.50	127282
溧水	124.3798883	19101	746805.52	177836
高淳	122.6924693	20267	370635.73	163623
常熟	127.1347257	25675	2194992	149593
张家港	124.873814	23108	2247736	201792
昆山	132.8408807	23307	3424092	242576
吴江	128.3784751	21879	2181670	149341
太仓	126.5423738	23762	1432235	183967
江阴	125.4371204	23423	2310984	242111
宜兴	124.4300019	20888	1510854	140905
丹徒区	122.9295245	17261	306472	126727
丹阳市	123.4269689	23526	899958	113081
扬中市	122.8593821	20658	495699	141646
句容市	124.0130109	18373	733999	105264
广陵	127.6021824	23441	433227	151803
邗江	130.9773766	20540	900226	151492
江都	120.183916	19604	1123536	107178
宝应	116.0174618	15187	775306	96410
仪征	120.5745561	16562	676784	138558
高邮	117.5343243	16678	799886	109978
高港区	123.6746143	18560	477000.00	240291
兴化市	117.9136062	15069	1112300.00	70178
靖江市	123.7489738	21570	862500.00	143066
泰兴市	120.0530121	15029	1064600.00	101157
姜堰市	120.5547508	16658	906000.00	96146
通州区	123.2190497	18651	1265600	121441
海安	122.504477	18665	1174100	131197
如东	117.3600914	16460	1325600	107740
启东	121.6260125	17794	1018100	121879
如皋	119.4875737	15906	1219400	98125
海门	121.9786979	18456	1128900	149375
沭阳县	115.7650221	12484	1195916	60572
泗阳县	115.0510828	13489	728776	59125
泗洪县	114.7383476	9825	895538	55111
宿豫区	114.919879	12484	479602	69464
宿城区	122.0056167	11844	450700	62986
淮安区	117.1604275	12138	798717	62081
淮阴区	118.4989434	15024	676866	66965
涟水县	111.6961817	10575	712989	62738
洪泽县	115.7276755	14230	406777	99665

盱眙县
金湖县

115.5950743
117.4252225

10149
16658

586994
478013

63805
97810

UI	Nre	Ieamw	Rurdi	
58.11	21.73		8180	1.74
57.9	43.06		7268	1.74
58.59	35.97		10442	1.62
59.84	34.44		6720	1.58
60.72	28.92		9341	1.70
62.55	48.1		9376	1.62
55.59	43.4		9324	1.81
48	42.7		7550	1.86
48.72	37.9		8693	1.74
51.72	29.5		6975	1.93
68.13867	37.96		16924	1.89
67.89519	21.22		19453	1.94
62.99738	32.22		16704	1.89
64.02839	20.99		18398	1.91
59.40746	9.38		15352	2.13
80.56704	27.99		20396	2.20
67.27652	26.01		21739	2.15
67.33155	18.14		15698	2.10
64.06963	21.87		13978	2.09
72.7985	38.37		22791	1.94
81.28917	32.88		19830	1.95
82.89097	21.11		21947	1.93
73.09884	29.78		19931	1.97
59.34938	15.04		21780	1.94
71.6	36.54		22143	1.92
66.1	36.47		18685	1.92
57.82033	14.48		14855	2.15
58.61947	36.51		17192	1.89
55.55581	13.59		19546	1.89
59.50948	27		13077	2.11
56.79425	10.99		21247	1.54
75.07427	17.01		17166	1.96
75.32792	42.26		14268	1.87
66.27907	40.75		12872	1.57
68.35126	22.84		13789	2.07
65.78342	36.55		12543	1.83
69.86	13.32		14006	1.99
56.96	60.58		11601	1.96
67.41	30.41		16532	2.00
63.45	56.81		12565	2.02
65.1	35.16		12323	2.09
62.98246	52.24		15015	2.02
61.88876	37.05		13067	2.05
59.97339	47.47		12664	2.14
61.11638	47.38		17585	1.87
60.48093	60.57		12255	2.14
63.1457	48.43		14648	1.93
58.13	76.5		10632	1.65
60.08	40.48		9189	1.65
59.41	37.99		8320	1.65
65.63	19.98		8135	1.64
64.55	24.25		9446	1.88
54.44667	44.51		10829	1.79
55.43797	38.78		11318	2.09
55.44554	48.57		7753	1.86
56.53881	16.21		8936	1.92

60.09146
56.88929

32.56
12.95

8803
9363

2.10
1.94

Nrle	Nntrl	Reb	Rf
	4785	13.15	0.70 0.5
	9096	28.08	0.67 0.494
	8357	21.92	0.68 0.486
	7412	22.48	0.77 0.552
	8171	19.89	0.80 0.486
	9057	30.08	0.61 0.502
	8471	28.10	0.7514 0.437788
	8279	24.80	0.7961 0.454333
	10922	18.90	0.7733 0.488127
	7925	16.70	0.70 0.481356
	3498	31.90	0.80 482086407
	2552	18.90	0.80 474081056
	3348	24.66	1.05 476412166
	1540	15.96	0.61 447355884
	777	7.67	0.71 468017058
	1340	22.88	0.61 483029653
	6395	20.89	0.66 462514418
	873	14.46	0.78 437155458
	2615	17.83	0.82 468678555
	1291	34.96	0.68 492276696
	1456	29.83	0.96 494136044
	2803	19.53	0.72 469282238
	1000	26.23	0.61 491236381
	994	12.43	0.72 490026596
	4649	32.59	0.81 0.465517
	4032	28.64	0.79 0.466959
	10728	11.32	0.74 0.494562
	1518	30.34	0.65 0.482296
	4041	11.75	0.74 0.492876
	3874	20.06	0.74 0.474697
	1319	9.84	0.84 0.474067
	2956	15.02	0.95 0.475015
	3953	36.27	0.85 0.467345
	4247	30.76	0.77 0.470429
	1284	19.64	0.77 0.468914
	1875	27.76	0.78 0.479617
	1713	11.64	0.62 0.509009
	14614	41.33	0.54 0.484483
	3864	25.67	0.52 0.485038
	9313	48.64	0.51 0.481605
	3165	29.83	0.59 0.520193
	6212	41.30	0.54 476837672
	8191	30.50	0.70 491767881
	7791	39.86	0.83 485780493
	13914	37.38	0.84 487336429
	12322	47.83	0.51 504375103
	953	37.83	0.66 479867851
	5652	50.87	0.85 0.475033
	1627	26.39	1.08 0.478014
	11540	17.86	0.91 0.474862
	6148	14.24	0.85 0.475475
	2427	15.65	1.03 0.462268
	2357	22.41	0.96 0.484835
	1882	24.27	0.97 0.445075
	14393	28.89	0.93 0.459955
	2537	10.39	0.52 0.490438

3829
2699

20.29
8.63

0.99 0.43059
0.90 0.467181

Plfis	Vlio	Ptam
0.357570179	845800	78.9
0.264514631	1226900	93.35
0.260494857	1198400	91.01
0.287166086	1747300	106.91
0.449170124	996700	67.46
0.323700624	2019200	102.03
0.32718894	506647	48.5573
0.318501171	1952104	165.4
0.229551451	1594793	129.11
0.33220339	523451	131.83
0.671232877	612240	23.5
0.778510839	311454	10.91
0.45965239	863358	56.56
0.511195808	689794	43.8
0.538379531	727806	26.31
0.555912826	1146220	52.22
0.465974625	1053350	56.84
0.49724366	800299	34.48
0.446273434	772198	54.66
0.80218921	682337	31.89
0.827554745	530283	30.15
0.839412601	513068	17.8
0.769308261	649344	23.6876
0.739361702	590934	21.32
0.770935961	598108	26.9995
0.619139018	803209	45.6759
0.627762431	383068	25.4038
0.70227335	812275	39.1655
0.78807947	284204	14.1426
0.464814815	787492	57.9401
0.705186533	92993	6.1669
0.553791887	196092	11.4549
0.485802177	575987	28.6623
0.442944785	691574	61.58
0.45709282	215087	42.37
0.491928865	775997.5	73.81
0.641891892	214830	12.972
0.748596897	2214179	126.94
0.755672476	421399	26.97
0.653582116	1033254	62.98
0.582195677	769217	45.3759
0.521056662	1044800	52.6826
0.542780027	1237900	70.2675
0.543290499	1670000	96.1744
0.484803715	1592300	65.6495
0.493808816	1189300	85.8996
0.526120173	1122800	40.0537
0.498169935	1827826	219.6422
0.456521739	1169311	111.372
0.305343511	1369103	169.0456
0.483483483	522898	64.87
0.403298969	417019	45.7495
0.289148506	1206397	104.396
0.39375967	1247154	84.8856
0.259419395	1145727	129.2841
0.433066009	724015	91.5224

0.373157248
0.412355212

1167464
783974

130.6385
76.3747

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0.737149063
0.76055725

0.77260524
0.814753463

region	Digital inclusive financial index Ce	Cf	GDP	
响水县	117.8089775	11882	714321.00	88861
滨海县	114.552658	12767	911482.00	61252
阜宁县	116.1880583	10387	914383.00	72498
射阳县	116.3514415	9698	961666.00	77221
建湖县	117.5710951	13205	913688.00	96503
东台市	120.9689533	15793	1183795.00	100495
东海县	118.0737927	11708	779964.00	53042
灌云县	115.6162695	10928	697113.00	52330
灌南县	116.9670831	10605	608057.00	64711
武进区	131.0450617	21612	1855644	153555
新北区	132.8825454	21132	815876	184697
溧阳市	125.3997946	20103	1161984	138302
金坛市	126.2004322	16780	871480	166294
浦口区	135.81996	20419	1688848.58	144840.8
江宁	136.1305802	21839	3239193.70	180246
六合	126.996585	20015	1518607.96	134312
溧水	126.9219112	18413	790039.73	185417
高淳	125.0261669	19740	392092.65	179360
常熟	128.2598157	24787	2297679	141308
张家港	126.7238544	22265	2332957	188045
昆山	133.9533636	22526	3656687	204737
太仓	128.0395028	22912	1510606	167382
江阴	126.8129741	22275	2378609	231239
宜兴	126.0296591	19906	1724446	142501
丹徒区	124.9865731	16571	318802	121185
丹阳市	125.4090726	22537	949998	115974
扬中市	125.3172448	19852	584505	155181
句容市	125.8616866	17620	789999	105766
宝应	118.0028144	14543	850604	111101
仪征	122.6622991	15901	685535	152660
高邮	120.3606691	15860	831678	117871
高港区	126.3115479	18476	48.90	635
兴化市	119.8000394	14699	114.76	901
靖江市	124.8510295	20191	106.21	1005
泰兴市	121.8381247	14674	108.34	1127
姜堰市	122.8969071	16400	80.06	687
通州区	124.1254679	17914	1375200.00	116758
海安	125.0321385	18381	1251300.00	139273
如东	120.2302185	16075	1348300.00	129381
启东	123.3445186	17585	1189900.00	126021
如皋	122.06334	15592	1251300.00	104858
海门	123.2688918	18265	1333500.00	146031
沭阳县	118.030104	12041	1322990	60609
泗阳县	117.951098	12984	877517	63578
泗洪县	117.988101	9447	992221	61001
宿豫区	117.4231436	12016	601935	75276
宿城区	123.9967642	11400	556017	60890
淮安区	118.9400327	11691	856469.00	616
淮阴区	119.1015049	14278	675783.00	550
涟水县	113.9525647	10211	730595.00	554
洪泽县	117.9117609	13765	505339.00	344
盱眙县	117.7923095	9791	641721.00	435
金湖县	120.2275068	16023	494824.00	337

UI	Nre	Ieamw	Rurdi	
	58.54	21.82	13467	1.690974147
	55.95	43.83	8380	1.704706453
	58.57	35.76	7623	1.584647147
	59.61	34.39	10974	1.548886653
	62.16	29.58	7165	1.661896853
	59.05	47.88	9938	1.59382748
	48.41	42.2	8040	1.815768423
	49.45	36.4	9424	1.692354808
	52.88	28.4	7293	1.883783155
70.21614936		38.37	17997	1.849927092
67.26367033		21.15	20619	1.888653329
63.11903246		32.05	17790	1.844164478
65.80656186		21.18	19634	1.870928632
64.08698397		9.48	16741	2.079039287
67.47337534		28.07	21940	2.154834459
60.45646081		25.81	23295	2.102705134
55.79728232		18.18	16810	2.054474173
59.14126222		21.84	14967	2.038784067
72.88940042	38.2689		23776	1.878599038
71.19913132	32.5693		21073	1.892843021
76.44544363	20.683		23359	1.866362213
72.69791044	14.9559		23105	1.881399749
	74.8	36.82	21607	1.879034777
	69.2	36.32	19994	1.883749615
68.02661605		14.5	15646	2.089072615
70.36212178		36.32	18292	1.841685881
64.90138605		13.59	20783	1.849171645
62.92547932		26.89	13783	2.057274215
67.28981445		40.45	13638	1.536305896
61.35053967		23.25	14713	2.00505388
61.91195681		36.52	13283	1.786403603
	69.58	13.31	14742	1.950751968
	57.60	60.54	12297	1.915560917
	68.43	29.12	17499	1.959512666
	62.25	56.87	13319	1.97139168
	63.90	32.79	13044	2.035845399
	64.61	52.09	16158	1.959868989
	68.76	36.986	14052	1.987766126
	58.2	46.688	13488	2.08492828
	59.98	46.9475	18875	1.819096933
	61.52	60.8531	13166	2.08135938
	66.74	48.355	15634	1.878161874
	58.88	75.06	11457	1.602137466
	61.54	40.5	9909	1.610420306
	61.16	36.15	8720	1.607555089
	66.98	19.84	8623	1.593187693
	65.18	24.75	9946	1.828933036
54.76787955		44.05	8351	1.74227216
57.25353994		39.62	8797	2.029397434
56.04435338		47.88	9563	1.813755293
59.64912281		16.11	8489	1.866349221
61.16600791		31.79	8119	2.033361762
60.2417962		12.88	9556	1.888760833

Nrle	Nntrl	Reb	Rf
5164		13.33	0.82 49.70
8264		29.22	0.78 49.80
7265		21.98	0.64 48.80
7019		22.60	0.7 54.90
6258		20.61	0.74 48.30
4799		30.24	0.65 50.10
6231		24.60	0.7420 0.45
6172		18.30	0.7826 0.49
8037		16.80	0.7621 0.49
3709		32.56	0.85 0.47
3015		18.85	0.81 0.47
2711		24.71	0.75 0.48
2118		16.27	0.74 0.45
1409		7.78	0.70 0.47
5586		23.03	0.61 0.48
3569		20.72	0.65 0.47
1858		14.52	0.79 0.44
2319		17.76	0.82 0.47
1585		34.95	0.65 0.49
1688		29.65	1.03 0.47
3761		19.12	0.75 0.49
1158		12.47	0.71 0.49
10618		32.88	0.83 0.46
8652		28.74	0.77 0.47
3319		11.47	0.735172414 0.49
2427		30.26	0.647852423 0.48
1762		11.85	0.752023547 0.49
6442		20.15	0.721829676 0.48
2195		30.52	0.781953028 0.48
3767		20.1	0.730752688 0.47
2525		27.9	0.78313253 0.48
1322		11.71	0.70 0.51
14646		42.03	0.70 0.48
4339		26.07	0.50 0.49
9391		49.06	0.50 0.48
3373		28.66	0.70 0.52
11812		41.46	0.523687848 0.48
8789		30.61	0.683547829 0.50
7312		39.30	0.832909955 0.49
9716		37.40	0.847297513 0.49
12031		48.34	0.487192929 0.52
4237		37.86	0.665405853 0.48
29674		50.84	0.827338129 0.48
9456		26.72	1.055802469 0.48
15830		17.82	0.916459198 0.47
4819		14.27	0.839717742 0.48
9189		16.90	1.002828283 0.46
14476		25.44	0.852213394 0.48
9636		25.31	0.962392731 0.45
4059		28.55	0.976190476 0.46
2335		10.49	0.528243327 0.49
5657		20.77	1.044039006 0.43
2561		8.60	0.901397516 0.47

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0.36	962900	80.9
0.26	1273400	98.82
0.27	1196400	91.5
0.29	1878200	108.33
0.44	954400	68.96
0.33	1373100	105.5
0.32	1864840	175.75
0.26	1778470	139.44
0.35	592780	132.95
0.69	641204	23.79
0.78	326111	10.47
0.46	904758	57.09
0.52	724741	43.85
0.53	755103	26.42
0.56	1186115	52.6
0.46	1093126	57.19
0.50	832720	34.89
0.45	810246	55.01
0.80	712529	32.3
0.83	550534	29.58
0.84	533513	17.86
0.74	486036	21.5
0.75	624887	27.0981
0.59	843255	45.6
0.631724138	402154	25.9855
0.705947137	862278	39.5572
0.795437822	298605	13.6332
0.466344366	851885	57.33
0.44	741350	64.96
0.46	228368	43.03
0.50	803679.5	74.54
0.76	226016	13.169
0.51	2321069	130.246
0.86	443788	27.5013
0.80	1090995	63.18
0.77	749145	46.0713
0.53	1107900	50.101
0.55	1343300	70.8
0.55	1794900	97.9852
0.49	1676800	67
0.50	1277300	85.8996
0.53	1216300	41.5
0.51	1895262	223.5024
0.46	1242582	116.4134
0.32	1490820	179.9049
0.49	548613	66.1674
0.43	457247	45.8
0.38	1286870	106.3
0.40	1341251	85.774
0.32	1228955	131.0497
0.44	770184	92.0574
0.39	1246983	133.7
0.42	826388	78.3747

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